

Analysis of Pride And Social Status: The Migrating Motive Minangkabau People In Cinema

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is this article is very interesting to analyze because it contains an exploration and description of the migration behavior shown in the film. then it is related to the behavior of the Minangkabau community. As a result, the change in the concept and motif of wandering in the film is a form of representation of the Minangkabau community's migration.

Keywords: *Minangkabau, film, representation, wander*

INTRODUCTION

In general, the word merantau for Minangkabau people, especially men, is not foreign anymore. Boys are required to migrate from a young age. This has become a hallmark of Minangkabau culture, namely how the Minangkabau culture interacts with outsiders. This definition of overseas wandering is related to the concept of geographical and cultural areas.

Rantau is a place to try, seek knowledge, experience, and results for happiness, well-being for oneself, relatives, and hometown. The history of Indonesian cinema cannot be separated from Minangkabau motifs. Most Indonesian films feature Minangkabau elements, such as the film Harimau Tjampa, the film Titian Serambut Dilih Tujuh, The Sinking of the Van Der Wijck Ship, Surau and Silek, and the film Tabula Rasa. The motif of wandering that is shown in these films is not only seen from the concept, but from the geographical side, motive, and background.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer us for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. The main sources in this study are 7 films that have Minangkabau

motifs in the content of the film, namely the film *Harimau Tjampa*, *The Pioneers of Independence*, *Titian Serambut Divisible Seven*, *Merantau*, *Under the Protection of the Kaaba*, *The Sinking of the Van Der Wijck Ship*, and *Surau and Silek*. This study focuses on the content and behavior of wandering that is obtained from the Action and narrative dialogue. In addition to the wandering aspect, on the other hand, this film also contains psychological and subjective narrative aspects.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study are films can be called representations. Storytelling is only compiling texts and narratives, but composing expressive ideas and ideas through various media. For example the film *Titian Serambut Di Belah Tujuh* (1982), this film is said to not represent the Minangkabau element. However, the film contains settings, characters, and messages that contain Minangkabau people. Meanwhile, in the film *Merantau* (2009) it is shown through the character Yuda. Yuda teaches Silek which is to practice the knowledge he has. Then in the film *Under the Di Bawah Lindungan Kaaba* (2011), the Minangkabau content in this film is found in the character of Hamid. Hamid continued his education at Thawalib Padang Panjang and taught at Surau, his village.

Tenggelamnya Kapal Van Der Wijck (2013) whose Minangkabau cargo was found in the warriors Sutan, Zainuddin, Muluk, and Rusli. The swordsman sutan went to Makassar out of shame and humiliation by his relatives associated with poverty. Then the character Zainuddin, the original character who came from Minangkabau, but the recognition of the village where the father was born is quite basic from Minangkabau. film *Surau dan Silek* (2017) the Minangkabau motif is presented by the characters Rustam, Irman, and Johar Hakim. Rustam migrated because he was ashamed to see his other friends wandering, in the end, he migrated to Yogyakarta, because on the other hand, migration was considered a cultural social behavior.

The purpose of this analysis of papers in the form of discussions is to know the Minangkabau motifs from the Indonesian film industry. The film is a representation and description of a condition that occurs in social and personal life. Minangkabau motifs in the film are conveyed directly or indirectly. In addition, there are differences in views and motives. You will see the difference when the film is released. The Minangkabau motif in the film ends by focusing on economic factors. Along with the development of overseas territories, they no longer looked at men to migrate.

The motive and motivation to migrate for men are to seek experience and learn. However, the motive for wandering is indicated by referring to family economic factors. Then shame and disappointment are always associated with society. Indirectly, economic factors influence overseas motives. The overseas motive in the film is no longer overseas in terms of seeking knowledge and experience. Instead, they wander in search of a living and look for a better life. Especially in economic life as well as financial needs.

CONCLUSION

For how the writer subjectively sees from the paper analysis that The reason the Minangkabau people migrated was because of the economy, geography, education, and politics. Regardless of the overseas motive, the Minangkabau community considers wandering a learning process and experience. Social changes both regionally, nationally, and globally, ultimately affect this wandering behavior.

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